

**The Practice and Contexts of Hub and District Leadership:
New Directions in Research on Educational Improvement Networks**

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ABSTRACT

Hub-centered improvement networks are emerging as an organizational form that has the potential to empower local educators, families, communities, and students to respond positively to ever-rising ambitions for educational access, quality, and equity in the United States. A problem, however, lies in a disconnect between (a) hub leaders as the linchpins of improvement networks and (b) the lack of a readily indexed research base to inform the study, practice, or evaluation of hub leaders and hub leadership. This article develops a theoretical foundation for such research by juxtaposing hub leadership in improvement networks with district leadership in public school districts. It asserts that differences in the organizational contexts, practical work, and ecological contexts of hub and district leadership are sufficiently stark to warrant investment in research focused specifically on the role and practice of hub leadership. It also frames considerations for such research

Keywords: hub leader, hub leadership, improvement networks, district leadership, educational leadership, continuous improvement, improvement research

**The Practice and Contexts of Hub and District Leadership:
New Directions in Research on Educational Improvement Networks**

This themed issue of the Peabody Journal of Education provides novel perspective on improvement networks as an emerging organizational form that has the potential to empower local educators, families, communities, and students to respond positively to ever-rising ambitions for educational access, quality, and equity in the United States. Our contribution explores the leadership of the hub organizations that serve as the operational centers of improvement networks. We conceptualize “hub leaders” as individuals and teams in the hub organization that share responsibility and accountability for the development, operations, and success of improvement networks. In turn, we conceptualize “hub leadership” as the practical work of hub leaders thus defined, as enacted individually and by teams.

As theorized in the introduction to this themed issue (Russell et al., 2025b), hub leaders are the linchpins of improvement networks, in that hub leaders establish and manage the contexts in which they and other network members define and pursue shared problems and aims. A problem, however, is that there has yet to emerge a readily indexed body of research to inform the study, practice, or evaluation of hub leaders and hub leadership. For example, at the time of this writing, an advanced search for “hub leader” + improvement + network + education using Google Scholar did not yield a single peer-reviewed journal article among the first 50 references returned. As yet, research on network leadership in the US has done little to discriminate among specific types of networks or different loci of leadership within networks.

If the networked improvement movement is to sustain and expand in the U.S., and unless its proponents and patrons are content with uncertainty in the knowledge base supporting its linchpin leaders, there is a need for readily identifiable research on hub leadership, beginning

with foundational research theorizing hub leadership as a category of educational leadership. Our purpose with this analytical essay is to address that need.

Our experience is that exploring a new concept like hub leadership benefits from analogizing with a more familiar concept. As such, we engage in a thought exercise juxtaposing hub leadership in improvement networks with an analog in K-12 public education: district leadership in public school districts. That both hub and district leaders are chiefly responsible and accountable for organizationally distributed educational enterprises suggests potential points of comparison. That one of these enterprises is novel (improvement networks) and the other conventional (public school districts) suggests potential points of contrast. One conjecture is that educational leadership is educational leadership agnostic of the enterprise being led, with little to distinguish hub and district leadership. Another is that hub and district leadership are sufficiently different as to warrant consideration as distinct categories of educational leadership.

We begin with a description of our analytical approach, and we continue with our comparison of hub and district leadership. Throughout, we accumulate evidence, analysis, and scholarship to support the assertion that, despite similarities as the chief leaders of organizationally distributed educational enterprises, differences between hub and district leaders are sufficiently stark to warrant research focused specifically on the role and practice of hub leadership. We conclude, then, by framing considerations for further research.

Analytical Approach

For our analysis, we began by putting district leadership in the first position and hub leadership in the second, as district leadership is the more familiar anchor. Recognizing that educational leadership has long been understood to be contingent on the contexts in which it is

situated (Hallinger 2018), we then compared district and hub leadership along three interdependent dimensions:

- The *organizational contexts* in which district and hub leadership are situated -- public school districts and their central offices (in the case of district leaders) and improvement networks and their hub organizations (in the case of hub leaders).
- The *practical work* of district and hub leaders in their respective organizational contexts, and the ways in which their practical work has emerged and evolved in interaction with their organizational contexts.
- The *ecological contexts* of hub and district leadership, and the ways in which diverse organizations, agencies, and interests in the broader environments of US public education have coalesced to legitimize and support district and hub leadership.

Our comparison is informed by three ongoing, collaborative programs of research that integrate scholarship, theory building, and empirical analyses, with the first author of this article the bridge between them. The first program of research examines the efforts of district and school leaders to build and operate instructionally focused education systems that aim to advance students' academic and holistic development (e.g., Cohen et al., 2018; Datnow et al., 2022; Peurach et al., 2019; Spillane et al., 2019; Yurkofsky & Peurach, 2023).

The second program of research is embedded within the Network Health Project on which this themed issue is focused (Russell et al., 2025b). This program of research focuses on the co-development of (a) a practical theory of hub leadership and (b) survey items on hub leadership for the Improvement Network Health and Development Survey (INHD Survey). Toward triangulating among interview, survey, and observational data, key activities have included:

- The development of a provisional framework detailing the practical work and associated challenges of hub leadership using interviews with 26 experienced hub leaders in 13 high functioning improvement networks (Peurach et al., 2020).
- The refinement of this framework in interaction with the iterative development of survey items on the work, challenges, contexts, and demographics of hub leaders over three administrations of the INHD Survey in 33 networks participating in the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation’s Networks for School Improvement (NSI) initiative (Duff et al., 2024).
- Ongoing participation in a community of leadership practice organized by the Gates Foundation to support the improvement networks funded under the NSI initiative.

The third program of research focuses on synthesizing the previous two, with the aim of providing novel perspective on the historical evolution of US public education in interaction with expanding societal, political, and policy ambitions for advancing educational access, quality, and equity (Peurach et al., 2018; Peurach et al., 2022; Peurach & Russell, 2024). This analytic essay is the next step in this third program of research, and the foundation of a forthcoming series of publications on hub leadership drawing on the evidence described above.

Working within our comparative framework across these three programs of research, our assessment is that district and hub leadership vary categorically along each of the three preceding dimensions. By that, we mean that district and hub leadership can be classified in ways that mark sharp, meaningful, and consequential distinctions in their organizational contexts, practical work, and ecological contexts. We develop these distinctions in more detail immediately below.

Comparing Organizational Contexts

The organizational contexts of district and hub leaders appear similar, in that both are situated in the central organizations of multi-organizational educational enterprises for which they are responsible and accountable: central offices and public school districts (in the case of district leaders) and hub organizations and improvement networks (in the case of hub leaders). Yet beneath these broad-stroke similarities, our analysis is that these organizational contexts are categorically different: the former as state-constituted, institutionalized, hierarchical professional bureaucracies; and the latter as variably constituted, temporary, networked adhocracies.

District Leadership

The organizational contexts of district leaders – public school districts – are geo-political enterprises constituted by state governments to administer schooling within their jurisdictions, with the legal mandate to serve all school-age children and youth by providing access to education. Public school districts first emerged in the late 1700s from local efforts to consolidate single schools into larger administrative units, and they were institutionalized through the first half of the 1800s as states incorporated provisions for public education into their newly created constitutions (Gamson & Hodge, 2016). In 2022/2023, there were 19,204 operating public school districts in the US (National Center for Educational Statistics, 2023).

As such, these organizational contexts are both ubiquitous and familiar. The entire country is served by some form of a public school district, with many Americans having first-hand experience participating in them as students and/or employees. Indeed, with only a small number of exceptions (e.g., charter school networks), districts leaders are more likely to be stewards of established educational enterprises than to be charged with creating them anew.

As institutionalized government agencies with formal authority over (and responsibility for) local schooling, public school districts are supported by institutionalized funding streams:

typically, a mix of local tax revenues, state per-pupil and other allocations, and supplemental federal grants (categorical, formula, block, and competitive). District leaders are responsible for securing and administering the funding needed to operate and sustain public school districts: for example, by championing local millages, sustaining student enrollments, applying for supplemental funding, and pursuing competitive grants. But, again, the sources of funding are both well established and formidable, with total funding for public elementary and secondary schools in 2019/2020 totaling \$870B (National Center for Educational Statistics, 2023).

Just as public school districts and their funding sources have become institutionalized over centuries, so, too, have their organizational structure and role structure: a conventional organizational template that integrates administrative hierarchy and professional bureaucracy in ways so homogenous and durable as to be famously characterized as “the one best system” (Tyack, 1974). As an administrative hierarchy, district central offices have formal authority over schools. Lateral operational relationships between schools are weak. Decisions flow “down” (e.g., about agendas, human resources, and financial resources), information flows “up” (e.g., about staff performance, resource usage, and students’ experiences and outcomes). As a professional bureaucracy, roles are differentiated within central offices and schools by specific responsibilities, requisite skills and expertise, and associated training and credentialing.

Individuals occupying district leadership roles are typically full-time employees of the district, with the leadership role structure paralleling the broader organizational structure. A single chief leader – the superintendent – serves under (and is directly accountable to) a democratically elected local school board (or, in some cases, a mayor). As districts increase in size, and as resources permit, the role structure is often elaborated to include functionally differentiated associate and assistant superintendents who report directly to the superintendent

and, possibly, functionally differentiated directors and coordinators that report either directly to the superintendent or an associate or assistant. District leaders have formal authority over school leaders. District and school leaders have formal authority over staff.

Formal administrative roles in districts (e.g., superintendents, and their associates and assistants) often require state certification for system-level leadership, prior experience in lower-level district and school leadership roles, and teaching experience. These prerequisites accord district leaders professional legitimacy to complement their legal, administrative, and positional authority. The presumption is that role-specific professional education, prior leadership experience, and prior educational experience have them well positioned to exercise authority in ways that comply with the laws, regulations, and policies of state and federal governments; that appropriately direct the leaders, teachers, and staff who serve under them; and that serve the educational aspirations and needs of students, families, and communities.

Hub Leadership

Thus, by the preceding analysis, one way to describe the organizational contexts of district leadership is as state constituted, institutionalized, hierarchical professional bureaucracies, with multiple (and strong) sources of leadership authority and legitimacy. By contrast, one way to describe the organizational contexts of hub leadership is as variably constituted, temporary, networked adhocracies, with fewer (and weaker) sources of leadership authority and legitimacy. As summarized in Table 1, this is an apt description of the improvement networks that participated in the Network Health Project.

Insert Table 1 about here.

Where public school districts have emerged and evolved for centuries, improvement networks of the sort featured in this themed issue only began emerging in the early 2010s. That

the Gates Foundation received 530 responses to the initial NSI call for proposals is evidence of enthusiasm for such improvement networks (Campisi, 2018). Even so, improvement networks are as yet niche educational enterprises, and nowhere near as ubiquitous and familiar an organizational context as public school districts.

Regarding their constitution, improvement networks are often established in one of two primary ways. The first is partnerships between “external” hub organizations that operate outside of the K-12 governance structure and one or more public school districts that operate within it. External hub organizations then recruit schools, teams within schools, or individuals within schools as network members. The second is within-district initiatives that establish or designate a team, group, or unit to function as an “internal” hub organization, with network members either recruited to the network from schools by the internal hub organization or assigned by the district. Both approaches have hub leaders constructing (rather than assuming stewardship of) the educational enterprises for which they are responsible and accountable.

Where districts are the institutionalized bedrocks of US public education, improvement networks thus constituted are what organizational scholars describe as “temporary organizations” anchored in newly established relationships among collaborating teams or organizations that share responsibility for defined projects, tasks, and objectives for pre-determined periods of time (Kenis et al., 2009). Temporary organizations are often premised on the expectation that their work will ultimately contribute sustaining value to the “permanent organizations” in which collaborators are situated, with returns on investment evaluated on those terms.

Three matters follow from the status of improvement networks as temporary organizations. The first matter is *funding precarity*. Rather than being supported by institutionalized funding streams (as with districts), improvement networks are typically funded

by supplemental discretionary resources within districts and/or by fixed term competitive grants. In the case of grants, any shared interest in collaborating beyond that fixed term requires that both hub organization and members (a) seek continuing funding and (b) adapt their priorities and administrative structures to coordinate with requirements of new funding sources. However, rather than well established and formidable (as is funding for public school districts), funding for improvement networks has thus far been scarce, unstable, and centered more in private philanthropy than in federal and state government (Peurach et al., 2022). Moreover, access to continuing funding is often predicated on demonstrating positive returns on prior investments, typically via rigorous evaluation of impacts on student outcomes.

The second matter is *allegiance precarity*. As temporary organizations, both the hub organization and network members are often situated within broader, “permanent organizations” as mentioned above: for example, a hub organization that operates as a special team within a non-profit organization, or an improvement team that operates within a school that is participating in the network. A consequence is that hub and network members maintain identification with, allegiances to, and responsibilities in their permanent organizations concurrent with participating in the network.

The third matter is *authority precarity*. Rather than legal authority over their educational enterprises (as in the case of district leaders), the formal authority of hub organizations and hub leaders is typically established via memoranda of understanding, contracts, and charges among (a) the permanent organizations within which hub organizations and hub leaders are located, (b) districts as the permanent organizations in which network members are located, and (c) funders.

The organizational contexts of hub leadership do not only differ from districts in their constitution. They also differ in their organizational and role structures. For example:

- Where districts are government agencies characterized by hierarchical relationships between central offices and schools, improvement networks of the sort featured in this themed issue aspire to function as scientific-professional learning communities characterized by reciprocal interdependence among hub organizations and members.
- Where the fundamental organizational make-up of districts always includes central offices and schools, the fundamental organizational make-up of improvement networks is comparatively varied: for example, with the constitution of either external or internal hub organizations, and with network membership consisting of schools, teams, or individuals either between or within districts.
- Where districts are characterized by professional bureaucracy with clearly delineated roles, responsibilities, qualifications, and authority relationships, improvement networks are characterized by adhocracy: adaptive, organic, often-informal organizational arrangements in which multi-disciplinary teams mobilize and organize diverse sources of expertise to solve complex problems in uncertain environments (Waterman, 1990).

As the primary bearers of responsibility and accountability for these adhocracies, hub leaders lack key points of leverage enjoyed by district leaders. For example, hub leaders do not have the same legal, administrative, and political authority of district leaders, nor the professional legitimacy that comes with ascending a leadership career ladder and associated certification requirements. Moreover, few hub leaders have extensive socialization in improvement networks as a ubiquitous and familiar organizational context. For example, of the 262 hub members who participated in the 2020/2021 administration of the INHD Survey, 48%

reported having zero to two years of experience in network leadership; 33% reported having three to five years of experience; and 20% reported having six or more years of experience.

Rather, hub leaders (again) have formal authority accorded them through memoranda of understanding, contracts, and charges; social authority through the meaning and significance ascribed to those agreements; complemented by whatever professional and reputational legitimacy that they bring with them from beyond the network. At this emergent stage in the networked improvement movement, the professional and reputational legitimacy of hub leaders is more likely to derive from their professional status and experience in other organizational contexts than from prior experience working in and leading improvement networks.

Comparing Practical Work

Thus, while each bears primary responsibility and accountability for an inter-organizational education enterprise, our analysis suggests that the organizational contexts of district and hub leadership are categorically distinct. This same pattern of “surface similarities and categorical distinctions” holds for their practical work.

In our analysis, the practical work of both district leaders and hub leaders focuses chiefly on building and operating their respective enterprises as *systems* in which technical methods, formal structures, social structures, and external relationships are developed and coordinated in positive, mutually reinforcing ways in pursuit of essential aims. However, the systems that they build and operate are categorically distinct. The work of district leaders focuses on building and operating *access-oriented school systems* and *instructionally focused education systems*. The work of hub leaders focuses on building and operating *practice-focused learning systems*.

District Leadership

In our research on district leadership, we frame the practical work of district leaders as having expanded over time to include two distinct tiers of functional responsibilities (Datnow et al., 2022; Peurach et al., 2019; Peurach et al., 2022; Peurach & Russell, 2024).

The first tier focuses on building and operating districts as *access-oriented school systems* that serve as contexts for the educational work of learning, teaching, and instruction. Such work includes administrative and managerial responsibilities: for example, building and maintaining schools; recruiting and retaining teachers and students; acquiring and distributing instructional resources; establishing and managing business systems; and ensuring compliance with legal and policy requirements. It also includes political and executive responsibilities: for example, establishing legitimacy and maintaining confidence among constituents; building consensus around visions and agendas; and securing and sustaining funding.

The second tier focuses on building and operating districts as *instructionally focused education systems* in which district leaders collaborate with school leaders and teachers to organize, manage, and improve learning, teaching, and instruction in ways that advance educational quality and reduce educational disparities. Such work includes:

- *Building educational infrastructure* that coordinates instructional designs, formal organizational resources (e.g., schedules, curricula, and assessments), and social organizational resources (e.g., norms, values, and relationships).
- *Supporting and integrating the use of educational infrastructure in practice* by developing teachers' professional knowledge and capabilities through such means as workshops, practice-based coaching and mentoring, and collegial learning.

- *Monitoring and managing practice and performance* in ways responsive both to policy requirements (e.g., annual improvement planning and teacher evaluation) and to weaknesses in instructional practice and student learning.
- *Managing environmental relationships* to discern, bridge, buffer, and reconcile influences bearing the pursuit of quality and equity in classroom instruction.
- *Developing and distributing instructional leadership* beyond established administrative positions to new leadership roles and structures responsible for performing, coordinating, and managing all of the preceding.

These two tiers of functional responsibilities have emerged historically, in response to expanding societal, political, and policy ambitions for advancing educational access, quality, and equity. The first tier – the work of building and operating access-oriented school systems – emerged and featured centrally in the work of district leaders from the early 1800s into the late 1900s, amidst a nearly two century-long period of sustained societal, political, and policy pressure to institutionalize universal access to mass public schooling. The second tier – the work of building and operating instructionally focused education systems – began emerging in the 1980s, as ambitions for public education expanded beyond ensuring equitable access to schooling to ensuring quality and equity in students’ education once in schools.

The addition of new, second tier responsibilities atop continuing, first tier responsibilities is a work in progress. Within districts, the work of building educational systems has been centered primarily in content areas that are the focus of state accountability initiatives (i.e., English/language arts, mathematics, and sometimes science), with different emphases among elementary, middle, and high schools. More aligned, coherent educational systems are emerging

in some content areas and levels of schooling; dysfunctional, legacy patterns in the organization, management, and improvement of instruction persist in others.

Hub Leadership

As framed above, the first and second tier work of district leaders focuses on supporting the learning and development of students by advancing ambitions for educational access, quality, and equity. By contrast, the work of hub leaders as theorized in this themed issue focuses on supporting the learning and development of district leaders, school leaders, teachers, and other educational professionals by building and operating *practice-focused learning systems* in which to address problems, needs, and opportunities that they experience in their first and second tier work (Russell et al., 2025a).

Indeed, these practice-focused learning systems are the improvement networks on which this themed issue is focused: scientific-professional learning communities in which members produce, use, refine, and manage knowledge through iterative analysis, design, implementation, and evaluation (Russell et al., 2025a). Beyond the technical problem solving and single loop learning that often characterize performance monitoring and management in education systems, these practice-focused learning systems are characterized, in principle, by adaptive problem solving and double loop learning in which members interrogate, disrupt, and reform school systems, education systems, and even the broader community and social systems in which districts are embedded (Peurach & Russell, 2024).

Building and operating practice-focused learning systems can be thought of as a third tier of functional responsibilities in districts over-and-above the first and second tier work of building and operating school systems and education systems. While this third tier work can be engaged by district leaders within conventional district structures (e.g., Honig & Rainey, 2020),

it is often either delegated or outsourced to hub leaders and improvement networks that operate either within or across districts.

This third tier work began emerging in the late 1990s and the early 2000s with initiatives and movements aiming to democratize educational innovation and improvement by empowering local actors to address educational matters viewed as meaningful and consequential in their local contexts, amidst policy-driven initiatives promoting evidence-based/evidence-proven interventions thought to be generally useful across contexts (Peurach et al., 2022). The work took on new meaning and urgency in the 2010s and 2020s, with the association of these movements and initiatives with calls for social justice in-and-through the work of inclusive, locally empowered educational innovation and improvement.

As described above in the Analytical Approach section, our contribution to the Improvement Network Health and Development Study has focused on developing a practical framework and associated survey items for studying the work and challenges of hub leaders in building and operating practice-focused learning systems. We have proceeded inductively and iteratively, beginning with interviews with experienced hub leaders to develop a provisional framework and, then, developing and refining survey items and the framework in interaction through three administrations of the INHD Survey (Peurach et al., 2020; Duff et al., 2024).

The preceding exploration suggests that the practical work of hub leaders includes the technical work of *supporting improvement activity within the network* by developing and modeling capabilities, routines, tools, and norms that support members in engaging in iterative analysis, design, implementation, and evaluation. Our exploration also suggests that this practical work goes further, to include additional domains of work reflective of the status of hubs and

improvement networks as temporary organizations operating in relation with each other, in complex educational, funding, and societal contexts. These domains of work include:

- *Developing and sustaining the hub as an organization*, including staffing and coordinating the hub team, building improvement capabilities in the hub, and analyzing and improving hub operations.
- *Building and managing the improvement network as an organization*, including building formal and social infrastructure connecting the hub and members, coordinating and managing activities among the hub and members, and coordinating with districts.
- *Integrating equity into the network*, including attending to equity both in developing the formal and social infrastructure of the network and in designing and pursuing improvement activities.
- *Managing relationships external to the improvement network*, including relationships with funders, evaluators, and the “permanent” organizations in which the hub and members are situated.
- *Analyzing and improving the network as a learning system*, in collaboration with network members and other stakeholders.

Consistent with our earlier analysis of hub organizations as adhocracies (and in contrast to professional bureaucracies with clearly differentiated roles), our analysis suggests that attention to these domains of work is not concentrated only in hub members who identified as having executive or managerial responsibilities commonly associated with leadership positions. Rather, attention to these domains of work is distributed among all hub members, including those who identified as having technical responsibilities. In effect, at least among the hub

organizations in the NSI initiative, to be a member of a hub organization is to engage in the practical work of hub leadership. For example, in the 2022/2023 administration of the INHD Survey, many hub members in leadership positions also engaged in technical work, and vice versa.

- Among 151 hub members who identified as having executive and/or managerial responsibilities, 54% reported that they always or often engage in the (ostensibly technical) work of supporting improvement activity in the network, and 22% reported that they sometimes engaged in such work.
- Among 101 hub members who identified as having exclusively technical responsibilities, 53% reported that they always or often engaged in the (ostensibly executive and managerial) work of developing and managing the network as an organization, and 27% reported that they sometimes engaged in such work.

As with the first and second tier work of district leadership, this third-tier work of hub leadership is complex and involves “constantly putting out fires” (in the words of a senior hub leader in an established, high-functioning improvement network).¹ Across our interviews and survey responses, we categorized this complexity as having roots in three primary sources: common challenges of “change management”, including maintaining commitment, focusing attention, and managing stress; the status of both hub organizations and improvement networks as temporary organizations, and the consequent authority, allegiance, and funding precarities described above; and “systems alignment” that coordinates the third tier work of building and

¹ See Neumerski and Yurkofsky (2024) for a complementary analysis of the complexity of hub leadership in two district-based improvement networks, with a specific focus on hub leadership as fraught with dilemmas that defy ready solutions and that require balancing competing (and often conflicting) values, goals, and expectations.

operating learning systems with the first and second tier work of building and operating school systems and education systems.

Managing the complexity of systems alignment is especially challenging in relation to the second-tier work of building and operating education systems as engaged variably by district leaders. Where engaged earnestly, hub leaders are challenged to coordinate with district leaders to add value to the work of building education systems, despite their authority precarity as leaders of temporary organizations. Where not engaged earnestly, hub leaders are often challenged to engage in improvement activity absent such essential resources as coherent and aligned instructional programs, assessment and data systems, and cultures and capabilities that support collaborative problem solving.

Comparing Ecological Contexts

Thus, our analysis suggests that the practical work of district and hub leaders centers on building and operating systems that, while operationally interdependent, are categorically distinct. This shared focus on building and operating systems is a response to the broader ecological contexts in which district leaders, hub leaders, and their educational enterprises are situated: a sprawling array of public and non-public organizations, interests, and initiatives that operate at the national, federal, and state levels to set agendas, advance policy logics, and allocate resources pressing districts to advance educational access, quality, and equity (Peurach et al., 2022; Peurach & Russell, 2024).

We continue by comparing ways that this ecological context has emerged and evolved to support the practical work of district and hub leaders in building and operating school, education, and learning systems. And, again, we find categorical differences: an institutionalized-and-

evolving organizational field supporting the practical work of district leaders; and an aspirational-but-precarious organizational field supporting the work of hub leaders.

District Leadership

Since the mid-1800s, a community of organizations in the broader ecology of US public education has coalesced and sustained as an institutionalized organizational field that prepares and supports district and school leaders as they assume their roles and responsibilities in state-constituted, hierarchal professional bureaucracies. Members of this organizational field interact to shape cultural-cognitive, normative, and regulative elements that, together with associated activities and resources, provide stability, meaning, and legitimacy to district leadership.²

This organizational field has emerged and evolved in reciprocal relationship with the expanding responsibilities of district leaders as described above. The field was first established in the mid-1800s under the banner of “educational administration”, with a focus on credentialing, legitimizing, and supporting the work of district and school leaders in building and operating access-oriented school systems. Beginning in mid-1980s and continuing to the present, the field has evolved and re-identified under the banner of “educational leadership”, signaling movement beyond administering districts and schools to organizing, managing, and improving districts and schools as instructionally focused education systems.³

Though specifics vary among states, the institutional infrastructure of the field educational leadership has evolved to include:

² We adapted this conception of an organizational field from Scott (2013).

³ We mark the origin of the field of educational administration with the establishment of the National Association of School Administrators in 1865. We mark the shift to educational leadership with such research and policy movements focused on *instructional leadership* (Murphy & Hallinger, 1986), *transformational leadership* (Leithwood, 1992), *distributed leadership* (Spillane et al., 2001), *equitable leadership* (Scheurich & Skrla, 2003), and *data-driven leadership* (Datnow & Park, 2014).

- Leadership preparation and certification through state-approved, university-based or alternative leadership preparation programs, with graduate degrees as either required or customary for formal administrative leadership positions.
- Accreditation of such leadership preparation and certification programs (e.g., as through the Council for the Accreditation of Educator Preparation), often contingent on alignment with national-level leadership standards as adopted/adapted by individual states (e.g., the National Educational Leadership Preparation standards).
- National-level membership organizations and their state affiliates (e.g., the American Association of School Administrators, the National Association of Elementary School Principals, and the National Association of Secondary School Principals).
- A research infrastructure as organized by the University Council for Educational Administration and the American Educational Research Association’s Division A (Administration, Organization, and Leadership).
- A multi-billion dollar industry that provides continuing professional education, translational research, textbooks, and technical resources and assistance that mediate among practice, research, and policy (Rowan, 2002).
- The National Policy Board for Educational Administration as a national-level “backbone organization” that forges field-wide coordination and cooperation.⁴

For purposes of our analysis, of particular interest in the evolution of the field of educational leadership is attention to the work of collaborative, continuous improvement of the sort that features centrally in practice-focused learning systems. Developments of this sort have potential to prepare district leaders and school leaders to serve as productive collaborators in

⁴ See Peurach and Cohen-Vogel (2022) on the role of backbone organizations in organizational fields.

improvement networks. They also have potential to position district and school leadership as pipelines to hub leadership.

While the concept and language of continuous improvement has gained currency with the shift from educational administration to educational leadership, the incorporation of continuous improvement into the institutional infrastructure of the field remains a work in progress. For example, it was only with the 2015 revisions to national standards for leadership preparation that continuous improvement was both (a) included as a stand-alone standard and (b) threaded systematically throughout the remaining standards and related performance indicators (National Policy Board for Educational Administration, 2018). The work of integrating these standards into the preparation of school and district leaders continues, as states adopt-and-adapt the standards; as universities redevelop their programs and their faculty to address them; and as accrediting bodies develop the understanding and capabilities to evaluate university programs and faculty.

Hub Leadership

Where district leaders are building school systems and education systems in institutionalized-and-evolving environments, the ecological contexts of US public education do not yet include analogous markers of an organizational field supporting hub leaders in building learning systems: for example, ubiquitous, improvement-specific graduate programs; requirements and standards for professional preparation and certification; established national-level membership organizations and state affiliates; or extensive research and technical assistance infrastructures. Rather, hub leaders are engaging the practical work of building learning systems at the same time that *institutional entrepreneurs* are engaging the *institutional work* of building the field of improvement in education (Peurach & Cohen-Vogel, 2022).

Indeed, since the mid-1900s, federal investment in education innovation has focused chiefly on funding external organizations in the ecological context to support the production and dissemination of basic research, applied research, and research-based/research-proven resources and interventions (Peurach et al., 2018; Peurach et al., 2022). To date, it has not included commensurate funding to organizations supporting the production, use, and refinement of practical knowledge in local contexts.

Even so, a collection of research initiatives in the 1980s and 1990s began exploring methods of design, problem solving, and knowledge production anchored in local educational contexts (e.g., Shulman, 1987, Brown, 1992; Cochran-Smith & Lytle, 1990; Collins, 1992). By the 2000s, further developments in and beyond the education sector seeded an “improvement movement” in education featuring formal approaches (e.g., improvement science, design-based implementation research, community-based design research, and participatory action research); organizational forms in which to enact these approaches (e.g., Networked Improvement Communities, design partnerships, and research alliances); and a range of motivating goals (e.g., increasing technical effectiveness, advancing educational equity, and empowering local communities) (Penuel et al., 2020; Peurach et al., 2022).

Beginning in the 2000s and accelerating in the late-2010s, a growing community of organizations has been leading efforts to expand the improvement movement while, at the same time, beginning to build a more coherent “field of improvement” distinct from (and that bridges to) the field of educational leadership. Early leaders included the Strategic Education Research Partnership, the Carnegie Foundation for the Advance of Teaching, and the National Center on Scaling Up Effective Schools. The community has since grown to include the Improvement Scholars Network, the High Tech High Graduate School of Education, the Improvement

Collective, the National Center on School-University Partnerships, the National Network on Education Research-Practice Partnerships (NNERPP), and the Improvement Science Special Interest Group in the American Educational Research Association (among others).

Rudiments of institutional infrastructure are beginning to emerge: for example, regular interaction among organizations representing diverse interests and constituencies; venues, convenings, and events supporting collegial interaction (e.g., the annual Carnegie Summit on Improvement in Education, the NNERPP Annual Forum, and the annual meeting of the American Educational Research Association); and the proliferation of trade books and translational research from academic and commercial publishers exploring and supporting the preparation and practice of improvement leadership in districts, networks, and hubs.⁵

Even so, these field building efforts are, again, a work in progress, and precarious. This aspirational organizational field as yet lacks a “backbone organization” to forge coordination, cooperation, and transparency; governance structures for setting shared agendas, reaching consensus, balancing individual vs. collective interests, and credentialing and legitimizing membership and activity; or a collection of funders committed to providing stable resources to support field building efforts across the full complement of organizations engaged in it.

In the absence of an institutionalized "field of improvement" in education, our evidence suggests that the professional preparation of hub leaders is characteristic of the type of emergent, temporary adhocracies described above. For example, of the 262 hub members who participated in the 2020/2021 administration of the INHDS, only 60% reported that they had any formal leadership preparation. Of those, 31% reported having either general leadership preparation or graduate degrees in fields such as business and public policy, while 69% reported having formal

⁵ For example, see Anderson et al. (2023); Anderson & Hayes (2023); Bonney et al. (2024); Bryk (2020); Bryk et al. (2015); Gomez et al. (2023); Hinnant-Crawford (2020).

training in the field of educational leadership and/or instructional, school, or district certification. Yet, as discussed just above, the field of educational leadership is just now evolving to institutionalize a focus on continuous improvement, and questions remain about the usefulness of such training for the practice of hub leadership.

A novel dimension of the NSI initiative was the construction of a Gates Foundation-funded ecosystem to provide hub-specific and network-specific technical assistance and professional development as a resource for participating networks. The ecosystem included funding for 20 “capacity building partners” to serve as resources for networks participating in the NSI initiative, included technical assistance providers, research brokers, leadership developers, data managers, and evaluators. Hub organizations were provided discretionary funding to engage capacity building partners on an as-needed basis, and they were required to engage a subset of capacity building partners to coordinate specific functions (e.g., data collection and evaluation).

The ecosystem also included a Community of Practice that convened hub leaders, leaders from network members, and capacity building partners at regular intervals. These convenings featured presentations from select hub leaders examining issues central to their practice, as well as opportunities for collaboration among hub leaders. Further, the convenings were typically designed to share information that was practical (vs. conceptual or theoretical), with support for hub leaders in applying the information in their own networks.

Hub leaders in the NSI initiative appeared to value professional development of the sort available in the foundation-funded ecosystem. For example, in the 2020/2021 administration of the INHD Survey, 165 hub leaders reported having had professional development on leading and operating networks. When asked in an open-ended question to describe the professional development that they found most valuable to their work as a network leader, 42% of the

responses described valuing professional development that was practical; 43% described valuing professional development that involved active learning with peers; and 46% described valuing professional development focused on core domains of practical work as described above.

While the foundation-funded ecosystem provides an image of the type of organizations and professional development opportunities that might characterize a more developed “field of improvement” in education, the ecosystem was, itself, temporary and precarious, and available only to networks participating in the NSI initiative. As the NSI initiative wound down, the foundation was devising ongoing means of continuing to broker relationships among capacity building partners and improvement networks in coordination with the broader field building efforts sketched above. How these field building efforts proceed, how they incorporate networks that did not participate in the NSI initiative, and how they interact with parallel developments in the field of educational leadership remain open matters.

Reflections: New Directions in Research

Our analysis focused on hub leaders as the linchpins of improvement networks. We began our analysis open to the possibility that there would be little to distinguish hub leadership from district leadership in public school districts. To the contrary, we accumulated evidence, analysis, and scholarship to support the assertion that differences in the organizational contexts, practical work, and ecological contexts of hub and district leadership are sufficiently stark to warrant investment in research focused specifically on the role and practice of hub leadership.

Indeed, our analysis suggests that hub leadership is a complex category of educational leadership that is situated within both (a) an historically novel organizational context and (b) a broader ecological context that as yet lacks stable funding and a coherent field of improvement to support it. As a consequence, even though they represent a select group that succeeded in

securing funding in a very competitive grant competition, our evidence suggests that many hub leaders in the NSI initiative had little prior professional preparation, development, or experience focused specifically on the work and challenges of hub leadership. On balance, this is not surprising, given the recent emergence of improvement networks over the past decade. Yet our analysis suggests that professional preparation, development, and experience in conventional district leadership is a questionable substitute.

But it is not clear what the preparation, development, and experience of hub leaders should include absent a robust, accessible research base focused specifically on the role and practice of hub leadership. To the extent that our analysis is persuasive, we close by drawing from it to suggest considerations for framing a comprehensive agenda for such research.

Specifically, we encourage further research on hub leadership that is:

- *Practical*, because of the immediate needs of hub leaders for useful knowledge, rigorous methods, and relevant professional development to inform and guide their work.
- *Contextual*, because the practical work of hub leaders is shaped by (and aims to shape) the organizational and ecological contexts in which it is situated.
- *Theoretical*, because framing the work and contexts of hub leadership in more general terms (e.g., temporary organizations, adhocracies, learning systems, and field building) bridges to other sectors and disciplines that have potential to provide new and deep insights.
- *Historical*, because the practical work of hub leaders is situated in, complicated by, and benefits from understanding decades- and centuries-long trajectories of progress and dysfunction in advancing ambitions for educational access, quality, and equity.

- *Instrumental*, because much needs to be understood about ways in which the development of hub leadership bears on the development of networks, the practice of improvement, and benefits for students.

We also encourage comparative research that continues to examine hub leadership in improvement networks in relation to district leadership in public school districts. As represented in our analysis, the practical work of district leadership is actively evolving in interaction with the broader field of educational leadership, with system-building and continuous improvement as themes central to this evolution. Further research comparing district and hub leadership has potential to advance knowledge about reciprocal interdependencies among school systems, education systems, and learning systems, as well as the practical work (and associated complexity) of building, operating, and aligning these systems. Further research comparing hub and district leadership also has potential to support the exchange of knowledge, ideas, and practices between these interdependent but distinct categories of educational leadership.

Finally, we encourage cross-national research that situates improvement networks in relation to initiatives in other countries that aim to democratize educational innovation and improvement. Educational networks are gaining currency in other countries in response to different national dynamics, with different network typologies, and with different designs and implications for leadership. Concurrently, these networks have become a keen focus of research. Consider, for example, research on Professional Learning Networks in Chile (Pino-Yancovic & Ahumada, 2020), school-to-school improvement networks in England (Greatbatch & Tate, 2019), and indigenous inquiry networks in British Columbia (Halbert & Kaser, 2022), as well as comparative research in Chile, England, New Zealand, and Singapore exploring alternative theoretical perspectives (Greany & Kamp, 2022). Further research conducted in collaboration

with global colleagues has potential to support the exchange of knowledge, ideas, and practices for advancing understandings of hub leadership in improvement networks.

A comprehensive research agenda of this sort would benefit from patrons of improvement networks recognizing that the return on investment that they typically value most – positive effects on and for students – depends on parallel investment in the theoretical and practical knowledge needed to realize those returns. Such recognition would, presumably, drive shifts in funding beyond customary impact evaluations toward a more diverse research portfolio. A comprehensive research agenda of the sort that we propose would also benefit from hub leaders who identify as “scholarly practitioners”, and who express a “bottom-up” press on funders for the theoretical and practical knowledge that they need to better understand their roles and contexts and to engage their practical work to greater effect.

Indeed, the other articles in this themed issue of the *Peabody Journal of Education* can be understood as positive returns on a patron (the Gates Foundation) that diversified its investment to include the production of theoretical and practical knowledge. Moreover, the INHD Study can be understood as an example of a community of practical scholars collaborating to provide a community of scholarly practitioners (the NSI hub leaders) with theoretical knowledge, practical knowledge, and real-time evidence to advance their understandings and their work. Where our contribution to this themed issue argues for the need for more (and novel) research, the other articles provide evidence of the possibility and value of producing exactly that.

Table 1

Organizational Context: Gates Foundation-Funded NSIs as Variably Constituted, Temporary, Networked Adhocracies

Characteristic	As reflected in Gates Foundation-Funded Networks for School Improvement
Variable constitution	15% of 33 networks that participated in the Network Health Project were managed by internal hub organizations in public school districts or charter school networks. 85% were managed by external hub organizations. Membership included school-based teams, cross-school teams, district-based teams, and a combination of district- and school-based teams.
Temporary organizations	Between SY 2018/2019 and SY 2020/2021, these networks were funded for five years to advance postsecondary outcomes for Black, Latinx, and/or low-income students. 37% of the networks were newly constituted; 63% built on pre-existing relationships between the hub organization and members.
Funding precarity	In 2020, the Gates Foundation announced a new 10-year strategy focused on K-12 mathematics and, with that, discontinued additional funding for the NSI initiative.
Allegiance precarity	55% of the external hub organizations operated as groups within non-governmental organizations or public technical assistance providers; 21% as groups within universities; 6% as alliances among groups in non-governmental organizations and universities; and 3% as alliances among groups in non-governmental organizations. 49% of the members of hub organizations reported having 50% or less of their time allocated to their work in their improvement networks.
Authority precarity	Formal agreements between the Gates Foundation, hub organizations, and districts included binding conditions related to funding, the use of funds, and evaluations, but no binding conditions establishing formal line authority of the hub over leadership, staffing, or improvement activity in network members. The participation of network members was voluntary, as was participation on member teams.
Adhocracy	Regarding diverse expertise, 262 hub members who participated in the 2021/2022 administration of the Network Health Survey reported 181 unique role titles in their permanent organizations. Regarding the lack of a conventional, clearly delineated roles, hub members reported 174 different role titles within their hub organizations. In the 2022/2023 administration, 34% of 298 responses reported an exclusive focus on executive, managerial, or coaching responsibilities; 36% reported a combination of executive, managerial, and/or technical responsibilities; and 21% did not identify with these responsibilities.

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